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Assessment of the Dampness Resistance of Asphalt Concrete using a Double Filler of Waste Engine Oil and Calcium Carbide Residue

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the moisture resistance characteristics of asphalt concrete with a dual blend of waste engine oil (WEO) and calcium carbide residue (CCR). The experimental design involved the adoption of Marshal Mix design method to prepare trial mixes with which optimum asphalt and WEO content of 5.4% and 0.3% were obtained. Preparation of CCR-modified samples involved addition of 2% to 10% CCR at 2% increments to partially replace aggregate by weighs. Marshall Stabilimeter was used to measure Marshall stability and Flow; conventional weight relationships were adopted to measure density and voids; while indirect tensile strength (ITS) indirect tensile strength ratio (ITSR), retained marshal stability (RMS) and swelling index (SI) in submerged conditions were obtained by applying relevant models. The results reveal that after submergence, ITS improved by 41% at WEO-CCR blend of 0.3% and 10% addition of CSA. ITSR after submergence was 79%, exceeding the benchmark of 75%. RMS improved with addition of WEO- CCR up to 10% under each category of submergence and stayed above the minimum threshold of 75% after submergence. SI also improved by 29.3% in addition of 10% CCR content. Therefore, it was established that WEO-CCR blend of 0.3% and 10% is optimum for enhancing moisture resistance properties. WEO-CCR combination is therefore recommended as alternative materials in pavement construction.

Keywords: *Moisture resistance, indirect tensile strength ratio, retained marshal stability, swelling index, hot mix asphalt*

INTRODUCTION

Road transport durability is a major concern in transport infrastructure, particularly in regions where environmental conditions accelerate pavement deterioration. Asphalt concrete remains one of the most widely used materials for flexible pavement due to its strength, flexibility and ease of construction. However, moisture-induced damage continues to be a significant factor affecting long-term performance of asphalt pavements, often leading to stripping, cracking and reduced structural integrity. In recent years, research has focused on improving the moisture resistance of asphalt mixtures through the incorporation of additives and modifiers. Among these, the use of industrial by-products and waste materials has gained increasing attention due to their potential to enhance pavement performance while promoting environmental sustainability. This study investigates the effectiveness of a dual blend of waste engine oil (WEO) and calcium carbide residue (CCR) in improving the moisture resistance characteristics of asphalt concrete under submerged conditions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Asphalt concrete properties, including its strength, moisture resistance, and durability, are influenced by the type and quality of the asphalt binder and aggregates used. The material's performance under various environmental conditions, particularly its resistance to moisture-induced damage, is crucial factor in determining the lifespan of pavements [1]. Modifications to asphalt concrete, such as incorporating polymer modifiers, fibers, or other additives, can significantly enhance its properties. These modifications can improve the asphalt binder's adhesive and cohesive strength, reduce permeability, and enhance the aggregate's resistance to moisture damage, ultimately leading to more durable and

resilient pavements [2].

Research on improving the moisture resistance of asphalt concrete is critical due to its widespread use in road construction and the significant impact of moisture on pavement longevity and performance. Current trends in moisture resistance studies focus on identifying additives and modifications that can enhance the durability of asphalt concrete against water infiltration and damage [3],[4]. These studies often explore both natural and synthetic additives, with a growing emphasis on sustainability and the use of waste materials to mitigate issues such as stripping, rutting, and cracking caused by moisture exposure.

According to Mohammed and Ismael [5], a relationship exists between asphalt moisture susceptibility and tensile strength ratio (TSR). Specifically, a higher TSR value corresponds to improved moisture stability of the asphalt, and TSR serves as an indicator of the asphalt mixture's sensitivity to moisture degradation. This viewpoint is corroborated by Wei *et al* [6], which revealed that samples immersed in water with varying levels of acidity displayed a declining trend in moisture resistance.

Incorporating waste engine oil and calcium carbide residue into asphalt concrete is an innovative approach aimed at improving moisture resistance while promoting sustainability. Waste engine oil, with its viscous and adhesive properties, can enhance the flexibility and durability of the asphalt binder [7]. A by-product of the manufacturing of acetylene gas, calcium carbide residue may be used as a filler to enhance the aggregate's qualities and lessen its susceptibility to moisture [8], [9]. The combination of these materials can potentially create a synergistic effect, enhancing the overall performance of asphalt concrete. This approach not only

addresses environmental concerns by recycling waste materials but also offers a cost-effective solution to improve pavement durability and longevity.

Ghabchi and Sheikhzadeh [10] investigated the impact of waste engine oil on the mechanical properties of asphalt mixtures, finding improvements in stiffness and resistance to rutting. Similarly, studies by Mashaan *et al.* [11] and Abbas *et al.* [12] examined the use of waste engine oil as a rejuvenator in aged asphalt, showing enhancements in stiffness modulus and fatigue resistance. However, challenges exist, particularly concerning the environmental and long-term performance aspects. Studies have raised concerns about the leaching of contaminants from waste engine oil into the environment and potential effects on pavement durability over time [13].

Wu *et al.* [14] demonstrated that CCR improves the stiffness modulus and rutting resistance of asphalt mixtures due to its filler effect and pozzolanic activity. The

presence of calcium hydroxide in CCR can also contribute to improved adhesion between asphalt binder and aggregates, enhancing overall pavement performance [15]. However, challenges exist, particularly related to the alkaline nature of CCR, which may affect the aging resistance and moisture sensitivity of asphalt binders. Research has shown that careful dosage and compatibility testing are crucial to optimizing the beneficial effects of CCR while minimizing potential drawbacks [16].

The primary aim of this study is to evaluate moisture resistance characteristics of asphalt concrete modified with a combination of Waste Engine Oil (WEO) and Calcium Carbide Residue (CCR) in submerged conditions. Specific objectives include the determination of Tensile strength, indirect tensile strength ratio, Retained Marshal Stability and Swelling Index of modified samples in submerged conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Materials

The materials used for this study, including their respective sources are shown in table 1

Table 1: Material and Sources.

S/N	Material	Source
1	Gravel	Building Material market
2	Sand	Building Material market
3	Asphalt Binder	Setraco Asphalt Plant, Elele
4	Waste engine oil	Local mechanic workshop
5	Calcium carbide residue	Gas welding workshop

Methodology

Material properties and classification

Material property classification tests were conducted in line with ASTM [17] and the following results were obtained:

Table 2: Material properties.

Materials					
Test	Bitumen	Gravel	Sand	WEO	CCR
Penetration (mm)	63.3	-	-	-	-
Specific gravity (G)	1.01	2.60	2.78	0.79	2.57
Softening point (°C)	52	-	-	-	-
Vaac. Capillary Viscosity	3.0	-	-	-	-
Mix proportion (%)	-	60	40	-	-

Table 3: Aggregates combination.

Sieve size (mm)	Upper Limit	Lower Limit	(%) passing A	(%) passing B	Mix proportion
19	100	100	100	100	100.0
12.5	86	100	95.7	100	97.4
9.5	70	90	62.5	100	77.5
6.3	45	70	15	100	49.0
4.75	40	60	1.5	99	40.5
2.36	30	52	0.5	95.8	38.6
1.18	22	40	0.5	88.1	35.5
0.6	16	30	0.5	77.5	31.3
0.3	9	19	0.5	25.4	10.5
0.15	3	7	0.5	3.4	1.7
0.075	0	0	0.5	0.3	0.4

Preparation of Samples

Samples were prepared according to the procedures for Marshall HMA Design as presented in Asphalt Institute [18]. The mix design procedure involves determining the appropriate proportions of aggregates (coarse and fine), and additives as demonstrated by Kim *et al.* [19]. Briquette samples were prepared following Schuler and Huber [20] using 4% to 6%

asphalt binder contents at 0.5% increments, to obtain optimum asphalt content (OAC) of 5.4%; which corresponds to the mean asphalt content that gave maximum stability, density and 4% air voids. However, a dual blend approach was adopted, such that WEO was added to the binder at 0.1% increments up to 0.5% as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Blending Schedule for Determination of Optimum Binder & WEO Content.

WEO (%)					
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5
Bitumen (%)	Proposed WEO-CCR Blends				
	A	B	C	D	E
4	4.0:0.1	4.0:0.2	4.0:0.3	4.0:0.4	4.0:0.5
4.5	4.5:0.1	4.5:0.2	4.5:0.3	4.5:0.4	4.5:0.5
5	5.0:0.1	5.0:0.2	5.0:0.3	5.0:0.4	5.0:0.5
5.5	5.5:0.1	5.5:0.2	5.5:0.3	5.5:0.4	5.5:0.5
6	6.0:0.1	6.0:0.2	6.0:0.3	6.0:0.4	6.0:0.5

Representative specimens were then cast using the OAC for both control mix and WEO-modified mixes. The WEO-CCR-modified mixes were prepared by addition of 2%, 4%, 6%, 8% and 10% CCR by weight of aggregates. Samples were prepared for several categories of

submergence in water ranging from 0 to 5 days. Upon completion of each soaking period, density and void analysis were conducted on the specimens. Afterwards, the Marshall Test apparatus was used to determine stability and flow at a temperature of 60°C.

Table 5: Mix design properties for trial mix.

Binder %	Stability (kN)	Density (kg/m ³)	Flow (mm)	VTM (%)	VMA (%)	VFA (%)
4	27.1	2337	2.20	6.700	12.5	46.2
4.5	27.6	2354	2.26	5.284	11.8	55.2
5	30.5	2364	2.53	4.141	11.4	63.7
5.5	30.6	2378	2.75	2.856	10.9	73.8
6	30.8	2359	2.93	2.913	11.6	74.9

Strength and Indirect Tensile Strength Ratio

Tensile strength and ITSr of the prepared specimens were obtained from the equations below.

$$ITS = \frac{2P}{\pi dt} \quad \text{Eq (1)}$$

$$ITSr = \frac{S_2}{S_1} \quad \text{Eq (2)}$$

Where: P = Load at sample failure

d = Diameter of sample (mm)

t = Thickness of specimen (mm)

S₁ = Indirect Tensile Strength of dry Specimen

S₂ = Indirect Tensile Strength of submerged specimen

Retained Marshall Stability

The Retained Marshall Stability measures the loss in Marshall Stability of the HMA after submergence and is expressed:

$$RSI = \frac{S_i}{S_o} \times 100\% \quad \text{Eq (3)}$$

Where; RMS = Retained Marshall Stability

S₀ = Stability of dry Specimen

S_i = Stability of submerged specimen

Swelling Index

The swelling index (SI) measures the percentage change in volume of specimens due to water absorption during the period of submergence. SI was obtained according to the

equation:

$$SI = \frac{V_2 - V_1}{V_1} \times 100\% \quad \text{Eq (4)}$$

and Volume (V) of the soaked specimen was obtained from the equation;

$$\frac{W_a - W_w}{W_a} \times 1000 \quad \text{Eq (5)}$$

Where; V1 = dry specimen volume

V2 = soaked specimen volume Wa = specimen weight in air Ww = specimen weight in water

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Indirect Tensile Strength

ITS of unmodified and WEO-CCR modified samples under various soaking categories is shown in Table 6 and Figure 1 (a & b)

Table 6: ITS of submerged samples.

Indirect Tensile Strength (N/mm ²)						
CCR	day 0	day 1	day 2	day 3	day 4	day 5
0%	3.09	2.99	2.75	2.72	2.35	2.23
2%	3.28	3.09	2.98	2.92	2.53	2.40
4%	3.37	3.33	3.09	3.07	2.63	2.52
6%	3.69	3.65	3.47	3.40	2.92	2.74
8%	3.75	3.74	3.64	3.45	2.98	2.83
10%	3.97	3.93	3.76	3.66	3.20	3.14

Fig. 1a: Graph of ITS against soaking days.

Fig. 1b: Graph of ITS against CCR.

Figure 1a and 1b shows that for the unsoaked category, σ_t increased by 28.5% from 3.09 N/mm² at 0% CCR content to 3.97 N/mm² at 10% CCR content. For samples soaked in water; after one day of soaking, results show that σ_t increased by 31.6% from 2.99 N/mm² at 0% CCR content to 3.93 N/mm² at 10% CCR content. For the five days soaking category, σ_t increased by 41% from 2.23 N/mm² at 0% CCR content to 3.14 N/mm² at 10% CCR content.

The results show the negative effect of submergence on tensile strength of HMA, which was observed to decrease steadily with increase in period of submergence. However, addition of CCR up to 10% minimized the impact of submergence on the mixture, while increasing its strength.

Indirect tensile Strength Ratio

Table 7 and Figure 2 (a & b) show the variation of ITSR of WEO-CCR modified HMA under various soaking conditions.

Table 7: ITSR of specimens after soaking.

ITSR (%)						
CCR	day 0	day 1	day 2	day 3	day 4	day 5
0%	100	96.7	88.8	88.0	76.0	72.0
2%	100	94.1	90.9	89.0	77.0	73.0
4%	100	98.7	91.7	91.0	78.0	74.6
6%	100	98.9	93.9	92.0	79.0	74.3
8%	100	99.7	97.0	92.0	79.5	75.4
10%	100	99.0	94.5	92.0	80.5	79.0

Fig. 2a: Graph of ITSR against soaking days

Fig. 2b: Graph of ITSR against CCR.

From Figures 2a and 2b; we can see that addition of WEO-CCR blends in varying percentages influenced ITSR for each category. After one day of submergence, ITSR was observed to range from 96.7% for the unmodified sample, to 99% for the CCR modified samples, representing a decrease of 3.3% after 24 hours. However, addition of 10% CCR ensured a 2.3% increase in ITSR compared to the unmodified mix.

After 5 days of submergence, ITSR was

observed to range from 72% for the unmodified sample, to 79% for the CCR modified samples, representing a decrease of 28% after 5 days. However, addition of up to 10% CCR ensured a 9.7% increase in ITSR compared to the unmodified mix.

Retained Marshall Stability

Table 8 and Figure 3 (a & b) show the variation of Retained Marshall Stability of CSA modified HMA under various soaking conditions.

Table 8: Retained Marshall Stability of specimen after soaking.

Retained Marshall Stability (%)						
CCR	day 0	day 1	day 2	day 3	day 4	day 5
0%	100	96.7	88.8	88.0	76.0	72.0

2%	100	94.1	90.9	89.0	77.0	73.0
4%	100	98.7	91.7	91.0	78.0	74.6
6%	100	98.9	93.9	92.0	79.0	74.3
8%	100	99.7	97.0	92.0	79.5	75.4
10%	100	99.0	94.5	92.0	80.5	79.0

Fig. 3a: Graph of RSI against soaking days.

Fig. 3a: Graph of RMS against CCR

From Figures 3a and 3b; we can see that addition of WEO-CCR blends in varying percentages influenced RSI for each category. After one day of submergence, the retained strength of modified mixture was observed to range from 96.7% for the unmodified sample, to 99% for the CCR modified samples, indicating that 3.3% of its strength has been lost after 24 hours. However, addition of up to 10% CCR ensured that compared to the unmodified mix, a 2.3% increase in RSI was observed. After 5 days of submergence, the retained strength of modified mixture was observed

to range from 72.0% for the unmodified sample, to 79.0% for the CCR modified samples, indicating that loss of strength ranged between 21% and 28.0 after % days. However, the addition of up to 10% CCR also guaranteed a 9.7% rise in RMS over the unaltered mix.

Swelling Index

Table 9 and Figure 4 (a & b) show the variation of Swelling Index of WEO-CCR modified HMA after submergence.

Table 9: Swelling Index of specimens after Soaking.

Swelling Index						
CCR	day 0	day 1	day 2	day 3	day 4	day 5
0%	0.00	1.511	2.248	3.436	4.010	4.363
2%	0.00	1.465	2.070	2.953	3.619	4.377
4%	0.00	1.348	1.820	2.434	2.794	3.549
6%	0.00	1.263	1.601	2.351	2.710	3.466
8%	0.00	1.087	1.425	2.311	2.670	3.426
10%	0.00	1.023	1.360	1.972	2.330	3.085

Fig. 4a: Graph of swelling index against soaking days

Fig. 4a: Graph of swelling index against CCR

Figure 4a and 4b show the changes in swelling due to WEO-CCR content and soaking condition for both modified and unmodified samples. Swelling index after one-day of submergence ranged between 1.02 and 1.51; indicating an increase of 32.3% after addition of 2% to 10% CCR. The lowest swelling index value was however observed at 10% CCR. This demonstrates that for the 24-hour soaking

category, the addition of CSA reduced the HMA's swelling potential by up to 10% CCR. SI varied from 3.09 to 4.36 after five soaking days, showing a 29.3% drop following the addition of 2% to 10% CCR content. For every soaking category, however, the lowest values were found at 10% CSA.

Overall, Swelling Index was observed to

increase as the period of submergence increased. However, lower values of SI after addition of WEO and CCR blends showed that the combination of WEO-CCR reduced the rate of influence of submergence on the modified HMA samples.

CONCLUSION

The indirect tensile strength of WEO-CCR modified mixes increased with CCR content addition up to 10%. Consequently, the indirect tensile strength ratio (ITSR) after 5 days of submergence was 79%, exceeding the minimum requirements of 75% for moisture resistance.

The Retained Marshall Stability (RMS) of WEO-CCR modified mixes, submerged in water, reduced with increasing period of submergence. However, 10% CCR content was sufficient to keep the index of retained strength at 79% after submergence which is above the permissible limit of 75%.

Swelling Index (SI) of WEO-CCR modified mixes, submerged in water, increased with increasing period of submergence. However, 10% CCR content was sufficient to reduce the swell index by 29.3% after submergence.

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